

Data Science automation: Current state and future trends

Asem Omari^a

^a *School of applied technology, Humber College, Canada*

Abstract

A successful data scientist need to have knowledge of the business context in addition to be expert in data analytics/science to understand the role of different models in making business decisions and be able to find the right model and the right data for the right question.

Taking into account the lack and huge demand for data analysts/scientists, hiring data scientists is considered an expensive and very difficult process and not within every company's means. As a result, Experts believe that machine learning is capable of automating many tasks related to big data analytics. Most of us already experienced the effects of big data analytics automation in our day-to-day lives in e-commerce websites like eBay web page personalization, Facebook friend Suggestions and LinkedIn recommendations.

In this paper, we discuss the current state and future trends of data science automation covering all phases of the knowledge discovery process starting from business question to knowledge extraction and investment.

Keywords:

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Data science; automation

Author biography

Asem Omari Asem Omari completed his PhD in data mining from Düsseldorf University in Germany. He has 10+ years academic experience teaching in different Colleges and Universities in Germany, Middle east and Canada. A dynamic and experienced data mining specialist with excellent knowledge in modeling, preprocessing, mining, managing and analyzing big data sets. He has a strong publication record of 16 publications in peer reviewed books, journals and conferences.

April 3, 2018